

2. B. ANJANEYULU, V. BABU RAO, A. K. GANGULY, T. R. GOVINDACHARI, B. S. JOSHI, V. N. KAMAT, A. H. MANMADE, P. A. MOHAMED, A. D. RAHIMTULA, A. K. SAKSENA, D. S. VARDE and N. VISWANATHAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 237.
3. F. M. DEAN, "Naturally Occurring Oxygen Ring Compounds", Butterworths, London 1963, p. 324.
4. S. HATTORI, *Nature*, 1951, 168, 788.

Chemical Constituents of *Woodfordia fruticosa* Linn.

JAGDISH S. CHAUHAN, SANTOSH K. SRIVASTAVA* and SAVITRI D. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

Manuscript received 19 January 1978, revised 12 April 1979, accepted 6 October 1979

WOODFORDIA fruticosa Linn (Lythraceae) is a shrub and found throughout India. The plant is reputed for its medicinal values^{1,2}. A perusal of literature revealed that no work has been reported on this plant. The present investigation deals with the isolation and identification of the constituents from flowers. The identity of each compound was established by comparison (m.m.p., IR, co-TLC) with authentic samples.

The air dried flowers (1.5 kg) of the plant, collected in Allahabad, were extracted with petroleum ether (40-60°). The extract was concentrated to 100 ml. On cooling it gave a yellowish coloured solid (500 mg) (Fraction-A). Then the defatted flowers were refluxed with ethanol (120 hr). The ethanolic extract was concentrated and poured into distilled water. The water soluble portion was extracted with ether (Fraction-B) and then ethyl acetate (Fraction-C) separately in a liquid-liquid extractor.

Hecogenin: Fraction-A, on column chromatography over neutral alumina and elution with methanol, gave a solid which on crystallization (aqueous methanol), furnished colourless white needles of hecogenin³ (300 mg) C₂₇H₄₂O₄, m.p. 253°, M⁺ 430. It gave positive Liebermann-Burchardt⁴ and Salkowski⁵ tests. ν_{max} (KBr) 3450 (OH), 2940 (CH₃), 1705 (CO), 1460 (C-CH₃) and 1350-875 cm⁻¹ (spiro-ketal side chain) etc., acetate, m.p. 250° (lit. m.p. 252°); 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 281-82° d. (lit. m.p. 282° d).

Mesoinositol: Fraction-B, on column chromatography over deactivated alumina and elution with ethanol, gave a creamish white solid (200 mg) which on crystallization (ethanol/petroleum ether mixture) gave colourless needles of mesoinositol⁶, C₆H₁₂O₆, m.p. 225-27°. ν_{max} (KBr) 3640 (OH), 1032 cm⁻¹ (OH) etc., acetate, m.p. 215° (lit. m.p. 216°), benzoate, m.p. 256° (lit. m.p. 258°).

* Correspondence Address: Dr. S. K. Srivastava, Chemistry Department, Saugar University, Saugar (M.P.) 470 003.

Flavone glycosides: Fraction-C, dark reddish coloured compound (2 g), on column chromatography over silica gel and elution with methanol: water in a gradient from (4:6) to (1:9) gave a mixture of three flavonoid compounds. This was resolved by preparative TLC with ethyl acetate: methanol in a different proportions into Band-I, Band-II and Band-III which afforded respectively Quercetin-3-rhamnoside⁷ (120 mg) as yellow needles (from aqueous methanol), m.p. 182-84°; naringenin-7-glucoside⁸ (110 mg) as golden yellow needles (from aqueous ethanol), m.p. 225-26° and kaempferol-3-glucoside⁹ (140 mg) as small yellow needles (from aqueous ethanol), m.p. 172-73°.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. R. D. Tiwari, Head, Chemistry Department, Allahabad University, Allahabad, for providing authentic samples and the U.G.C., New Delhi, for research fellowship to one of us (SKS).

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA., *Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants*, 1956, 259.
2. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU., *Indian Medicinal Plants*, 1940, 2, 1074.
3. R. E. MARKER, R. B. WAGNER, P. R. ULSHAFFER, E. L. WITTBECKER, D. P. J. GOLDSMITH and C. H. ROUF., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1199; 1947, 69, 2167.
4. C. LIEBERMANN., *Ber. deutsch. Chem. Ges.*, 1885, 1804.
5. E. SALKOWSKI., *Hoppe-Seylers Z.*, 1908, 57, 521.
6. S. BROWNSTEIN., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 1606.
7. A. G. PERKIN and A. E. EVEREST., *The Natural Organic Colouring Matters.*, Longmann Green & Co., London.
8. W. RAHMAN, M. ILLYAS and N. HAMEED., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 278.
9. T. NAKABAYASHI., *J. Agr. Chem. Soc.*, Japan, 1952, 26, 539.

Chemical Constituents of *Anemone narcissiflora* Linn

K. P. TIWARI*, M. MASOOD and Y. K. S. RATHORE

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad, India

Manuscript received 12 January 1978, revised 7 December 1978, accepted 6 October 1979

A large number of saponins¹ have been isolated from various species of the genus *Anemone*, but surprisingly, complete structures of these saponins have not been elucidated. The authors, therefore, undertook the chemical analysis of *Anemone narcissiflora* Linn.² with a view to make a detailed study of saponin and other constituents of the plant. The present paper deals with the isolation and characterisation of oleanolic acid, betulinic acid, β -sitosterol, β -amyryn and a new saponin olean-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl- $\Delta^{1,2}$ -ene-28-oic acid from *A. narcissiflora*.

Procedure and Results

The air dried and powdered plant material (2 kg) was exhaustively extracted with ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. The thick viscous mass so obtained was extracted repeatedly with hexane to remove chlorophyll and fat. The defatted residual mass was extracted with ether. The ether extract on evaporation of the solvent yielded a solid mass. The solid mass was resolved into acidic and neutral fractions by the usual potassium salt method³. The acidic fraction was dissolved in chloroform and passed through a column of silica gel. Elutions with a mixture of methanol and chloroform (1 : 2), yielded compound A, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$, m.p. 316-8° M⁺ 456 and compound B, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$ m.p. 308-10°; M⁺ 456, identified to be betulinic acid and oleanolic acid respectively by comparison of their spectral data⁴ and m.m.p. with the authentic samples.

The neutral fraction was dissolved in chloroform and passed through a column of silica gel. Successive elutions with mixtures of petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) and benzene : chloroform (1 : 1) yielded compound C, $C_{30}H_{50}O$, m.p. 198-200° and compound D, $C_{30}H_{50}O$, m.p. 134-36° identified as β -amyrin and β -sitosterol respectively by comparison of i.r. spectra⁵ and m.m.p. with the authentic samples.

The defatted residual mass left after the extraction with ether, was dissolved in methanol and poured into large quantity of ether whereby a dark brown coloured flocculent mass precipitated. The process of dissolution and precipitation was repeated several times in order to purify the coloured mass. It was then decolourised by boiling the methanolic solution of the coloured mass with activated charcoal and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to dryness and the solid mass so obtained was dissolved again in a small quantity of methanol and poured again in large quantity of ether whereby a white flocculent mass was precipitated. The precipitate was separated by filtration. On repeated crystallisation from methanol colourless crystals of compound E, $C_{30}H_{48}O_7$, m.p. 206-8°, were obtained, which gave the tests characteristic of saponins⁶. The saponin was hydrolysed with 7% ethanolic sulphuric acid whereupon the sapogenin was precipitated. The sapogenin was separated from the hydrolysate in the usual way and was crystallised from methanol. The sapogenin, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$, m.p. 308-10°, has been characterised as oleanolic acid by comparison of spectral data and mixed m.p. with the authentic sample. The sugar moiety has been found to be rhamnose by co-chromatography with the authentic sample. The quantitative estimation of sugar in the hydrolysate by colorimetric method⁷ revealed the presence of one mole of sugar per mole of saponin. The saponin could not be hydrolysed with 5N NH_4OH which indicates that the COOH group of sapogenin is not involved in glycosidic linkage⁸. Therefore, the OH group at C-3 of oleanolic acid is involved in glycosidic linkage with L-rhamnose. The titrimetric estimation after periodate oxidation of the saponin has revealed that the sugar moiety attached to the

sapogenin is in the pyranose form⁹. Thus, compound E is olean-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl- Δ^{12} -ene-28-oic acid.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Dr. D. S. Bhakuni, C. D. R. I., Lucknow, Dr. T. R. Govindachari, Dr. R. S. Grewal and Dr. S. Selvavinayakam, CIBA-GEIGY Research Centre, Bombay for their kind help in the spectral studies of the compounds reported in this paper.

References

- (a) G. LUFT, *Monatsh*, 1926, 47, 259; (b) J. BALANSARD and J. DELPHAUT, *Med. Trop.*, 1945, 15, 322; (c) A. BIENFAIT, *Bull. Ordre Pharmaciens*, 1960, 15, 167; (d) Huang et al., *Chem. Abs.* 1964, 61, 4699.
- R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, 'Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants', C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 19.
- F. D. DODGE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 40, 1917.
- (a) K. P. TIWARI, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1972, 42, 86; (b) H. BUDZIKIEWICZ, J. M. Wilson and C. DJERASSI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3688; (c) H. BUDZIKIEWICZ, C. DJERASSI and D. H. WILLIAMS, 'Structure Elucidation of Natural Products by Mass Spectrometry', Holden-Day, San Francisco, 1964, Vol. II, p. 121.
- S. P. TANDON, K. P. TIWARI and A. P. GUPTA, *I. O. and S. J.*, 1969, 164.
- C. H. SANNIE, *Anal. Biol. Chem. Med.*, 1948, 9, 175.
- S. B. MISRA and V. K. RAO MOHAN, *J. Sci. and Ind. Res.*, 1960, 19, 173.
- V. HARIHARAN and S. RANGASWAMY, *Phytochemistry*, 1970, 9, 409.
- E. L. HIRST and J. K. N. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1659.

Flavonoid Constituents of the Leaves of *Polygonum glabrum*

K. P. TIWARI*, M. MASOOD and R. D. TRIPATHI

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad, India

Manuscript received 19 July 1978, revised 7 December 1978, accepted 6 October 1979

THE plant *Polygonum glabrum* (N. O. Polygonaceae) a small shrub, is widely distributed throughout India¹. The infusion of leaves is used in colic pains and the plant is used as febrifuge². The literature survey of the genus *Polygonum* shows that it is a rich source of flavonoids³⁻⁸ and the flowers of this plant have been examined chemically for the anthocyanins and flavones⁹.

Procedure and Results

The air dried, powdered leaves of *Polygonum glabrum* (2 kg) were extracted exhaustively with ethanol. The alcoholic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to a thick viscous mass. This was